

Who Benefits from School Selection?

Kaire Põder¹, Faisal Mohammed¹ & Triin Lauri²

1. Estonian Business School, Estonia
2. Tallinn University, Estonia

Summary

1. We examine how three school selection mechanisms – early tracking, elite tracking, and lottery-based school choice – affect student achievement.
2. Early tracking has a small negative average effect on achievement, especially in reading.
3. Elite tracking shows only small gains for students near the admission threshold, with limited evidence of wider system benefits.
4. Lottery-based school choice has no clear average effect, but may benefit low-achieving students while not helping high achievers.
5. Selection policies are not neutral: they involve political choices about which students receive better opportunities and how others are protected.

1. Introduction

Student achievement has fallen in many OECD countries, and the decline is not limited to disadvantaged students. High-achieving students have also experienced substantial losses. This has renewed policy interest in how education systems organise students across schools and pathways. One long-standing question is whether selection helps schools teach students better by grouping them according to ability, or whether it increases inequality by giving some students access to better learning environments while leaving others behind.

This policy brief summarises a recent BRIDGE paper by Põder et al. (2026) on three common

school selection mechanisms: early tracking, elite tracking, and school choice by lottery. Early tracking separates students into different educational pathways, such as academic or vocational tracks, usually between ages 10 and 14. Elite tracking refers to admission into academically demanding or prestigious schools, often through tests or prior grades. Lottery-based school choice allows families to apply to preferred schools, but allocates places randomly when schools are oversubscribed. These mechanisms differ in who makes the decision: teachers and schools, parents, or a random allocation rule.

The central question is not simply whether selection “works”. The more important policy question is who benefits, who loses, and which trade-offs policymakers are willing to accept. Selection policies affect who learns

with whom, which teachers students encounter, and what school environment they experience. For this reason, selective admission is never just a technical design issue. It is also a political choice about whose learning opportunities are prioritised.

Pöder et al. (2026) ask what the cumulative causal evidence says about the effects of selective practices on achievement in mathematics, reading, and science, and whether these effects differ for low- and high-achieving students.

2. Previous Evidence Base

Existing literature reviews show that early tracking is generally linked to lower average achievement and higher inequality of opportunity. When students are separated into different school tracks at a young age, disadvantaged students are more likely to be placed in lower tracks. This can limit their access to demanding curricula, high-achieving peers, and later educational opportunities. For this reason, early tracking is often seen as a risk for both equity and overall performance.

The evidence on elite tracking is more mixed. Some studies find small gains for students who just pass the admission threshold and enter selective or academically demanding schools. However, these effects are usually limited and do not necessarily translate into wider benefits for the whole education system. Existing reviews therefore suggest that elite tracking may help some selected students, but its broader system-level impact remains uncertain.

For lottery-based school choice, previous evidence points to weak positive effects. Lotteries can make access to oversubscribed schools fairer, especially when they replace

informal or socially selective admission practices. However, the expected achievement gains are generally modest and depend strongly on the quality of the schools students gain access to.

Overall, existing meta-studies provide useful evidence on the average effects of these selection mechanisms. However, they pay less attention to whether the effects differ between low- and high-performing students. This is an important gap, because selection policies may benefit some groups while leaving others unaffected or worse off.

3. Data and Methodology

The study brings together causal evidence from the last two decades. It focuses only on studies that use experimental or quasi-experimental methods, meaning that they are designed to estimate the effect of selection rather than simple correlations. The review started from more than 72,000 sources and, after excluding studies that did not meet the criteria, ended with 23 causal studies: 6 on early tracking, 12 on school choice by lottery, and 5 on elite tracking.

The included studies examine students aged 15 or younger at the time of exposure and report achievement outcomes in mathematics, reading, or science. When possible, the analysis distinguishes between low-achieving and high-achieving students. Low-achieving students are defined as those below PISA proficiency level 2 or in the bottom quarter of the achievement distribution. High-achieving students are defined as those at PISA level 5 or above, or in the top quarter of the achievement distribution.

Because studies use different tests and report results in different ways, Pöder et al. (2026)

convert all findings into a common scale. It then combines the evidence in a way that accounts for the fact that one study may report several results across subjects, cohorts, or student groups. In plain terms, the study estimates the overall effect of each selection mechanism while taking differences across studies seriously.

4. Results

The evidence shows that average effects can hide important differences between students. A policy may have a small overall effect while helping one group and harming another. This is the main reason why selection policies should be judged by their distributional consequences, not only by average achievement.

Early tracking has a small negative average effect. Students in systems that track before age 12 score about 0.10 standard deviations lower than comparable students in delayed-tracking or comprehensive systems. The negative effect is strongest in reading, where the estimated decline is larger than in mathematics or science. However, the evidence by achievement level is more nuanced. For both high- and low-achieving students, the effects are small and not statistically clear. The overall negative effect may therefore be driven mainly by middle-achieving students, who are not separately examined in the subgroup analysis.

Elite tracking shows only a small positive effect for students near the admission cut-off. This means the evidence mainly concerns students who just gained access to an elite or selective school. The study does not provide strong evidence that expanding elite tracking would raise achievement across the whole system. It also cannot fully show what happens to students left behind in non-elite

schools. This limitation matters because elite tracking may concentrate resources and high-achieving peers in selected schools while weakening the learning environment elsewhere.

Lottery-based school choice has no clear positive average effect. It appears more promising for low-achieving students, who show moderate gains, but it does not help high-achieving students and may even slightly harm them. Pöder et al. (2026) therefore interpret lotteries more as an equity mechanism than as a policy for academic excellence. Overall, the evidence does not support a simple “selection is good” or “selection is bad” conclusion. Selection creates trade-offs.

5. Policy Recommendations

First, policymakers should avoid using average achievement alone to judge selection policies. Every reform should report expected effects for low-, middle-, and high-achieving students. This is especially important because the evidence shows that the same policy can benefit one group while offering no gain, or even possible losses, for another. Selection reforms should therefore include clear equity and excellence indicators from the start.

Second, early tracking should be delayed where possible, especially when students are separated before age 12. The average effect is negative, and early decisions may be too strongly shaped by family background, teacher expectations, and unequal access to support. If tracking remains in place, systems should keep pathways flexible, allow movement between tracks, and provide strong support for students who are not placed in academic routes.

Third, elite tracking should not be expanded as a general achievement policy without safeguards. The evidence shows only small gains for students near admission thresholds, and it says less about the students who do not enter elite schools. Selective schools should therefore be accompanied by transparent admission rules, outreach to disadvantaged students, and monitoring of effects on non-selected schools.

Fourth, lotteries can be useful where the goal is fair access to oversubscribed schools. They can reduce unfair gatekeeping and may help lower-achieving students access better school environments. However, lotteries should not be presented as a policy for excellence. High-achieving students may need additional curriculum enrichment, advanced learning opportunities, or targeted support that random allocation alone cannot provide.

Finally, policymakers should make the trade-offs explicit. The key question is not whether school selection works in general, but which students receive preferential treatment and how the system protects those who do not.

school selection mechanisms: A multilevel meta-analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18772161>

What is BRIDGE ?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

References

Pöder, K., Mohammed, F., & Lauri, T. (2026). Causal effects of educational between-

Figures

Figure 1. Results across three selective practices

Notes: $^\dagger p < 0.10$; $* p < 0.05$; $** p < 0.01$; $*** p < 0.001$. I^2 : percentage of total variability across studies attributable to heterogeneity rather than sampling error; low for early tracking (12%), high for elite tracking (83%), very high for school choice (97%). τ^2 : estimated variance of true effect sizes across studies, measuring the absolute magnitude of between-study heterogeneity. All effect sizes are Hedges' g (standardised mean difference). Random effect meta regressions used.

Further Information:

Pöder, K., Mohammed, F., & Lauri, T. (2026). Causal effects of educational between-school selection mechanisms: A multilevel meta-analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18772161>

**Funded by
the European Union**

BRIDGE is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101177154). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Follow us online www.bridge-horizoneurope.eu

Follow us on Bluesky [@bridgeproject.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/bridgeproject.bsky.social)

Follow us on LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/bridge-horizon-europe-project